

Pericardial Injury: Obstructive and Septic Shock Secondary to Penetrating Thoracic Trauma: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

This case involves a 23-year-old male patient who sustained a left hemothorax trauma caused by a puncture object. Initially, the injury was managed as a simple left pneumothorax, and the patient was discharged in improved condition. However, 48 hours after the initial intervention, he re-presented with clinical signs consistent with obstructive and septic shock. Diagnostic evaluation revealed purulent pericarditis. An urgent surgical procedure was performed, including thoracotomy and creation of a pericardial window, to drain the purulent fluid accumulated in the pericardium. The patient was subsequently admitted to the intensive care unit and later transferred to the general hospital ward. Following a favorable clinical course and resolution of infection and shock signs, he was discharged in stable condition and good overall health.

KEYWORDS: obstructive shock, pericardial diseases, pericardial window, cardiac tamponade, thoracotomy, emergency department, surgery, penetrating injury, thoracic trauma, septic shock management.

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INTRODUCTION

Penetrating thoracic injuries can induce hemodynamic instability, necessitating immediate medical interventions. Patients initially presenting in a stable condition may experience rapid deterioration, making prompt and accurate assessment essential to identify potentially life-threatening conditions [1]. Thoracic injuries are a common cause of preventable death in trauma patients, with approximately 10-15% requiring surgical intervention [2]. Specifically, among patients with penetrating injuries, it is estimated that between 15% and 30% will need surgical resolution, while in blunt trauma, about 10% of patients will require intervention [3]. Cardiac injuries occur in approximately 0.16% of thoracic trauma cases and are associated with mortality rates reaching up to 35% [4]. Pericardial effusion can present in various forms, including transudate, exudate, purulent pericarditis, or hemothorax. Effusions that develop insidiously may be asymptomatic, whereas those that occur acutely can cause

cardiac tamponade even with small volumes of accumulated fluid [5].

CASE PRESENTATION

A 23-year-old male with a history of substance use presented with a puncture wound in the left parasternal third intercostal space. Upon admission, the patient was asymptomatic, and a FAST ultrasound performed at the scene showed no pathological findings. During his hospital stay, he maintained a favorable clinical course and was discharged. However, 48 hours later, he was readmitted with hemodynamic deterioration, systemic inflammatory response syndrome, and chest pain. A repeat FAST ultrasound was positive (FIGURE 1).

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FIGURE 1: USG FAST (P) Pericardium, (PF) Pericardial fluid & (H) Heart.

Faced with the diagnosis of cardiac tamponade, an urgent left anterolateral thoracotomy was performed under balanced general anesthesia. A hemothorax of approximately 100 cc was identified, and the pericardium was notably enlarged, containing approximately 200 cc of purulent fluid, which was sent for microbiological culture (FIGURE 2).

FIGURE 2: Anterolateral left thoracotomy.

The findings indicated a punctate cardiac injury classified as grade III according to the AAST classification.

Repair was achieved with a U-suture using Monocryl 3-0 in the affected myocardial tissue (FIGURE 3).

FIGURE 3: Sutured heart. (M) Monocryl.

Subsequently, pericardial cleaning was performed via the pericardial window, and a 36 French pleural drain was placed for cavity closure. Postoperative management in the intensive care unit included broad-spectrum antibiotics, NSAIDs, and goal-directed resuscitation. Postoperative electrocardiogram showed ST-segment elevation, while cardiac enzymes normalized. The patient exhibited a favorable clinical evolution within the first 24 hours, with decreased pleural output, allowing removal of the pleural drain at 72 hours post-surgery. The patient completed a 10-day antibiotic regimen and was discharged without complications.

DISCUSSION

Cardiac tamponade is a complication in which the accumulation of fluid in the pericardium causes compression of the myocardium, increasing intrapericardial pressure and impairing cardiac function [6].

Purulent pericarditis, although rare in the adult population, represents a potentially fatal condition if not treated promptly. Predisposing factors include pericardial effusions, immunosuppression, chronic diseases, history of cardiac surgery, and thoracic trauma [7].

The etiology can be traumatic [8] or medical in origin, presenting with acute symptoms in traumatic cases and with a low-grade inflammatory process in medical cases. Electrocardiography (ECG) may reveal various alterations in patients with cardiac tamponade, such as low voltage, PR segment changes, ST-T segment abnormalities, and bundle branch block. On chest X-rays, severe pericardial effusions can manifest as globular cardiomegaly with sharp and well-defined borders [9].

The clinical presentation is typically acute and fulminant, characterized by rapid symptom progression. Therapeutic management includes drainage of the pericardial cavity and antibiotic therapy. The preferred surgical approach is subxiphoid pericardiotomy via open surgery, which has an approximate operative mortality rate of 8% [9].

In this clinical case, the patient was initially diagnosed solely with thoracic trauma due to the absence of classic symptoms associated with cardiac injury. He was subsequently discharged after apparent clinical improvement. However, he later required a second hospitalization where the diagnosis of cardiac tamponade secondary to bacterial pericarditis was established. The therapeutic intervention consisted of a surgical

approach via anterolateral thoracotomy with creation of a pericardial window to relieve compression and drain the septic content [10, 11].

The patient suffered penetrating trauma wounded pericardium and myocardium without presenting tamponade at that time (Grade II). Subsequently, he developed cardiac tamponade due to purulent pericarditis [12]. (TABLE 1)

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Table 1: Scaling system for organ specific injuries. Focused in Heart Injury.

Heart injury scale	
Grade	Description of injury
I	Blunt cardiac injury with minor ECG abnormality (nonspecific ST or T wave changes, premature arterial or ventricular contraction or persistent sinus tachycardia) Blunt or penetrating pericardial wound with out cardiac injury, cardiac tamponade, or cardiac herniation
II	Blunt cardiac injury with heart block (right or left bundle branch, left anterior fascicular, or atrioventricular) or ischemic changes (ST depression or T wave inversion) without cardiac failure Penetrating tangential myocardial wound up to, but not extending through endocardium, without tamponade
III	Blunt cardiac injury with sustained (≥ 6 beats/min) or multifocal ventricular contractions Blunt or penetrating cardiac injury with septal rupture, pulmonary or tricuspid valvular incompetence, papillary muscle dysfunction, or distal coronary arterial occlusion without cardiac failure Blunt pericardial laceration with cardiac herniation
IV	Blunt cardiac injury with cardiac failure Penetrating tangential myocardial wound up to, but extending through, endocardium, with tamponade Blunt or penetrating cardiac injury with septal rupture, pulmonary or tricuspid valvular incompetence, papillary muscle dysfunction, or distal coronary arterial occlusion producing cardiac failure Blunt or penetrating cardiac injury with aortic mitral valve incompetence Blunt or penetrating cardiac injury of the right ventricle, right atrium, or left atrium Blunt or penetrating cardiac injury with proximal coronary arterial occlusion Blunt or penetrating left ventricular perforation Stellate wound with $< 50\%$ tissue loss of the right ventricle, right atrium, or of left atrium
V	Blunt avulsion of the heart; penetrating wound producing $> 50\%$ tissue loss of a chamber

Based on the literature review and clinical observations made, it is recommended to implement rigorous hospital monitoring for patients with penetrating thoracic injuries-even when initial diagnostic tests such as FAST or computed tomography (CT) are negative. This is especially relevant given that bacterial pericarditis secondary to trauma is an infrequent but potentially fatal entity.

Thanks to timely clinical intervention during re-admission and appropriate surgical drainage that eliminated the obstructive infectious focus and controlled septic shock, the patient demonstrated favorable clinical progress. Two main types of shock were identified: obstructive and septic. The obstructive shock was managed surgically and resolved satisfactorily; since it carries a higher mortality rate compared to septic shock originating from the pericardial focus, its resolution was prioritized. Subsequently, the patient underwent periodic evaluations at 2, 6, and 12 weeks postoperatively and was eventually discharged from care.

CONCLUSIONS

The clinical management of a patient with penetrating thoracic trauma requires prompt, coordinated intervention carried out by a highly experienced multidisciplinary team with in-depth knowledge of the variety of injuries that can occur in this type of trauma and that pose potentially life-threatening risks to the patient. In hemodynamically stable patients, it is essential to perform a thorough evaluation using a focused assessment with sonography for trauma (FAST) exam and a chest computed tomography (CT) scan, complemented by continuous hospital monitoring to detect any signs of clinical or hemodynamic deterioration.

In cases where hemodynamic deterioration is observed, it is imperative to consider the presence of shock in its various clinical forms, including cardiogenic, obstructive, hypovolemic, or septic shock. Early identification of the type of shock and its underlying cause is crucial for determining the most appropriate therapeutic strategy. Early surgical exploration can be decisive in these scenarios, as depending

on the specific diagnosis and clinical assessment, it may offer significant benefits by enabling immediate identification and correction of potentially fatal injuries.

Therefore, decisions regarding surgical intervention should be made promptly and based on clear clinical criteria, always considering the patient's hemodynamic status and available diagnostic findings. Timely surgical exploration not only facilitates control of internal bleeding or major structural injuries but also helps prevent severe complications resulting from delays in appropriate treatment.

The management of patients with penetrating chest trauma should be rapid and performed by an experienced team familiar with all possible life-threatening injuries. Hospital observation is recommended for patients with penetrating chest injuries even if the initial FAST ultrasound is negative. A follow-up FAST ultrasound should be performed at 24 and 48 hours after the trauma, because bacterial pericarditis from trauma is rare but can be fatal.

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